

Tailored Aligned-Carbon Nanotube Nanocomposites for Energy Storage

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1 Introduction

The storage and release of energy has long been a challenge. Batteries can store large quantities of energy in a small volume, but their energy release rate is slow, which leads to a low power density and finite lifetime [1,2]. Dielectric capacitors, on the other hand, have high power density (i.e. can be charged and discharged at high rates), but their ability to store energy is limited, and so their energy density is low [3,4]. Supercapacitors have the potential to bridge the gap between these technologies, providing both high power, and mid-high energy, with relatively long lifetime [3,5-8]. Such a capability would make these new-generation devices very attractive for advanced applications such as renewable energy storage and hybrid electric vehicles, which in turn demonstrate the need to achieve even higher energy and power density [9-12].

Aligned carbon nanotubes (A-CNT) have promising features as nanoporous electrodes for supercapacitors; very high surface area, superior electrical conductivity pathways, and parallel ion-pathways which could improve the ion transport via accessible and non-tortuous

pathways. Indeed, morphology-controlled A-CNT based supercapacitor electrodes exhibit the potential for much higher power and energy density than those based on activated carbon or randomly packed CNTs [13,14].

Nevertheless, as-synthesized A-CNT forests are far from being ideal supercapacitor electrodes – the low nanotube volume fraction (~1%) will result in low volumetric electrochemical performance due to relatively low surface area, and the relatively inert chemical nature of CNT (much like that of graphite) will eliminate the possibility of chemically-enhanced pseudo-capacitance, thus reducing the potential for higher energy storage. It is therefore clear that much more research is needed to allow supercapacitors to utilize such materials to achieve the desired improvements in gravimetric and volumetric power and energy densities.

For example, if the A-CNT could be grown, or packed, into higher volume fraction, than the per-volume performance would increase significantly, just by providing higher surface area for the same volume. Indeed, several groups have tried in the past decades to find

ways densify the as-grown A-CNTs to high CNT density in order to achieve high volumetric capacitance, energy density, and power density. Futaba et al., to name one attempt, introduced a liquid collapsing method to densify A-CNTs in which the surface tension of liquid forces the A-CNTs to collapse to a high density [18].

Beyond high packing of the A-CNTs, the addition of conducting polymers (CP) to the supercapacitor electrodes will contribute to improved energy storage capability due to the redox process occurring throughout the whole volume of the CP material, in sharp contrast to the stored charges on the CNT electrode surface only [15], thus enhancing the effective surface area of the electrode [16]. A conformal coating of conducting polymer on the A-CNTs will therefore provide pseudo-capacitive electrodes with large energy power densities, but the right method needs to be found in order to enable this highly important conformal coating; up to now, the electrochemical methods used for deposition of conducting polymers on CNTs result in non-uniform CP layers on the CNTs and are incompatible with the A-CNTs (or generally nanowires) considered here [16].

In this work, we present two complementary approaches to increase the specific capacitance of A-CNT based supercapacitors. Using a unique mechanical densification method, we show that increased volume fraction improves the electrochemical performance, especially for the volumetric metrics. Moreover, for a given volume content of A-CNTs, we show that coating conducting polymer (CP) increases specific capacitance of the cell over a range of discharge current densities.

It should be pointed out that the volumetric energy density and power density are critical parameters to characterize practical capacitive performance of supercapacitor cells, and so this paper focuses mainly on volumetric properties.

2 Experimental

This section provides technical details on the materials and methods used in the current study.

In this study, A-CNTs were grown via a procedure used in previous work [17]. Briefly, small-diameter multiwalled CNT arrays (“forests”) were grown by thermal catalytic chemical vapor deposition (CVD) on silicon wafers using a thin catalyst layer of Fe/Al₂O₃ deposited by electron beam evaporation. The CNT growth was performed in a quartz tube furnace at 750 °C using ethylene as the carbon source. Typically, CNT arrays are grown on 1 cm² silicon dies, resulting in a 1% volume fraction (V_f) of CNTs having an average diameter of 8 nm in a CNT-forest (99% air). For the higher volume fraction A-CNT fabrication, a mechanical biaxial densification process was used [14], and different volume-fractions were attained by varying the inter-CNT distance in the densification process. The difference between as-grown and densified A-CNTs can be seen in Fig. 1.

Alternatively, the above as-grown A-CNT forests were used to fabricate poly(ethylenedioxythiophene) (PEDOT) /A-CNT composites using a modified chemical vapor deposition method (oCVD) previously published [14], which can produce conformal nanometer-thick coatings of CP into the high

aspect ratio A-CNT arrays. Briefly, EDOT was polymerized using iron chloride as the oxidant, which was then reacted with the EDOT monomer (supplied through the vapor phase) that resulted in the formation of a PEDOT film on the CNT array substrates. Different coating times than described previously [14] were used, in order to allow different coating thicknesses, up to ~4nm. Cross-sectional SEM images of a CNT array after coating with PEDOT are presented in Fig. 2. As observed in Fig. 2 the orientation and shape of the CNT bundles in the array are not disturbed by oCVD of the PEDOT coating process.

A-CNT composite supercapacitors were then assembled and a porous paper with 40 μm thickness was used as separator, immersed in an ionic liquid/molecular liquid mixture (IL/ML) used as the electrolyte (see Fig 3 for illustration). Supercapacitor electrodes of activated carbon powders (Sigma-Aldrich) were also fabricated using the standard method reported in the literature and characterized [18] as a comparative baseline.

The electrochemical performance of the capacitive electrodes were evaluated by the cyclic voltammetry (CV) and galvanostatic charge-discharge tests using a screen-printed electrode system (Dropsens) where the A-CNT based electrode with a platinum current collector was the working electrode, while silver and platinum were used as the reference and counter electrodes, respectively. An example of the electrochemical performance of supercapacitors with A-CNT electrodes (different V_f percentage, no CP coating) can be seen in Fig. 5.

3 Results and Discussion

The results of the electrochemical performance measurements for the various morphologies of A-CNT based electrodes, as well as discussing their meaning and further implications, are presented in the following sections.

3.1 Effect of volume fraction

The effect of the CNT volume fraction on the electrochemical performance of A-CNT based devices is discussed in this section. Fig. 4 presents the volumetric CV curves at 100 mV/s scan rate of supercapacitors with different A-CNT volume fractions and with EMI-BF₄ as the electrolyte. The capacitance of the A-CNT based devices can be deduced by integrating the half CV curve and is also specifically presented in Fig. 5. A marked increase in the volumetric capacitance is exhibited when increasing the A-CNT volume fractions from 1% to 20%. It is thus clear that densification will indeed significantly increases the volumetric specific capacitance.

Fig. 5 shows the specific capacitance (a) and Ragone plots (b) for the A-CNT based supercapacitor cells under 3 V. As shown in Fig. 4 (a), the electrodes with 1% V_f of A-CNTs show a low volumetric capacitance, (~ 1 F/cm³). The mechanical densification method developed here preserve the nanomorphology of the ion channels so that the volumetric capacitance of 20% V_f A-CNT electrode is up to 13 F cm⁻³. The energy of the cell in each discharging cycle, E , is determined by integrating the discharge curves.

$$E = \int IV(t)dt \quad (1)$$

The power density can be deduced from,

$$P = \frac{V^2}{4 * ESR} \quad (2).$$

where V represents the operation voltage, while ESR can be deduced from the voltage drop as the current is switched from a positive value to a negative value, divided by the change in the current. The specific volumetric power density can then be obtained by normalizing to the cell volume.

As shown in Fig. 5 (b) the supercapacitor cell with 20% V_f A-CNTs electrodes exhibit a higher volumetric energy density (5 Wh/L) and power density (> 5 kW/L) than at 1% V_f . The electrochemical performance of the ultra-high density A-CNTs electrodes fabricated from the mechanical densification method demonstrate the preservation of the nanomorphology that allows aligned ion pathways. Therefore, the denser packing of CNTs maintains the ability to achieve fast charge/discharge rates along with high power and energy densities.

The 20% V_f A-CNT supercapacitors also exhibit an excellent cycling life as shown in Figure 6. The data was acquired over 5000 cycles by repeating the galvanostatic charge/discharge process between 0 and 3 V at a current density of 5 A g⁻¹. As clearly seen, the supercapacitors with the ultra-high density A-CNTs show an excellent electrochemical stability with retention of 98% after 5000 cycles, thereby demonstrating the high mechanical integrity of the CNT-based electrodes, establishing relatively long operating times with little hysteresis for such supercapacitor architectures.

3.2 Effect of conducting polymer coating

This section investigates the effect of different thicknesses of conducting polymer coating on the electrochemical performance of A-CNT composite based devices. Fig. 7 presents the specific capacitance at different discharge current densities, from 0.5 A g⁻¹ to 10 A g⁻¹. High capacitance retention of 50% and more was obtained at 10 A g⁻¹ (from 195 F g⁻¹ at 0.2 A g⁻¹ to 107 F g⁻¹ at 10 A g⁻¹ for the X4 coated A-CNT electrode), indicating that the A-PEDOT/CNTs electrode provides reliable capacitive performance for high power applications. Since large energy density at high charge/discharge current is required for high performance energy storage devices [19], the high retention rate of the composite electrode is extremely promising for applications. Moreover, since the electric conduction path of the continuous aligned CNTs is unaffected by mechanical failure of the CP coating layers due to high currents, PEDOT/A-CNT electrodes should exhibit a robust mechanical stability that contributes further to the high retention of the capacitance not only at high current density, but also over a longer lifetime, than purely CP-based electrodes.

It should also be noted that increasing the CP coating thickness also increases the specific capacitance at any current density, but somewhat reduces the relative retention rate. The increased capacitance is likely attributed to both the increased effective surface area created by the thicker CP layer and the pseudocapitance created by the chemical interactions within the polymer, and enhanced due to the larger availability of reactants. However, the polymer is likely to be current-

sensitive, and so will most likely fail to respond under high current rates, reducing the available reactive layer into similar to that of the uncoated A-CNT forest and limiting the retention. Further research needs to be done in order to explore the mechanism behind this behavior.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This paper demonstrates the possibilities lying in the densification of A-CNT forests to extra high volume fraction, or coating them with CP, in the fabrication of highly efficient supercapacitors. Maintaining the nanomorphology of the aligned ion pathways, which enables high ion mobility in the electrodes, is the main advantage of the A-CNT morphology, but higher CNT volume fraction, as well as the addition of a pseudocapacitance mechanism via CP-coating, enables even higher performance.

Indeed, supercapacitor cells with 20% V_f A-CNTs of 0.8 mm electrode thickness exhibits excellent electrochemical performance, including a volumetric power density and energy density of 5 kW L⁻¹ (23 kW kg⁻¹) and 5 Wh L⁻¹ (22 Wh kg⁻¹), respectively, which are much higher than that of supercapacitors with activated carbon electrodes [18]. Also, high CP coating thickness (up to 4 nm thickness coating) also improves significantly the electrochemical performance, showing high specific capacitance with 195 F g⁻¹ as well as high retention over large range of currents and cycles. Future work will be to combine these nanomorphological features in combination to further tailor electrochemical performance of supercapacitors.

5. Figures

Fig. 1a: A-CNT forest, as-grown (1% V_f) [20].

Fig. 1b: A-CNT forest, densified (20% V_f) [20]. The spacing between CNT is significantly smaller, suggesting higher surface area per-volume.

Fig. 2a: PEDOT coated A-CNT. The coating time was twice that detailed in previous work [14].

Fig. 2b: PEDOT coated A-CNT. The coating time was four times the process detailed in previous work [14].

Fig. 3: A schematic of the A-CNT based supercapacitor illustrating the collimated and continuous ion paths between the A-CNTs in the electrodes.

Fig. 4: Volumetric cyclic voltammograms of A-CNT electrodes with 1% and 20% V_f at 100 mV/s.

Fig. 5b: Ragone plot (volumetric) of supercapacitors with 1% and 20% V_f A-CNTs at 3 V in volumetric power and energy density.

Fig. 5a: Volumetric specific capacitance for the supercapacitors with 1% and 20% V_f A-CNTs at different discharge rates.

Fig. 6 Cycle performance of 20% V_f A-CNTs supercapacitor with a voltage of 3 V at charge and discharge current density of 5 A g^{-1} .

Fig. 7 Gravimetric specific capacitances for the supercapacitors based on 5% V_f pure A-CNTs and different coating thickness of PEDOT/A-CNTs electrodes at different discharge rates.

References

- [1] J. Garche, "Advanced battery systems—the end of the lead–acid battery?" *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* Vol. 3, pp 356-367, 2001.
- [2] P. Thounthong, S. Rael and B. Davat, "Energy management of fuel cell/battery/supercapacitor hybrid power source for vehicle applications" *J. Power. Sources.* Vol. 193, No.1, pp. 376-385, 2009.
- [3] A. G. Pandolfo and A. F. Hollenkamp, "Carbon properties and their role in supercapacitors" *J. Power. Sources.* Vol. 157, No.1, pp.11-27, 2006.
- [4] B. Chu, X. Zhou, K. Ren, B. Neese, M. Lin, Q. Wang, F. Bauer and Q. M. Zhang, "A Dielectric Polymer with High Electric Energy Density and Fast Discharge Speed" *Science* Vol. 313, No.21, pp.334-336, 2006.
- [5] A. Nishino, "Capacitors: operating principles, current market and technical trends" *J. Power. Sources.* Vol. 60, No.2, pp.137-147, 1996.
- [6] S. Nomoto, H. Nakata, K. Yoshioka, A. Yoshida and H. Yoneda, "Advanced capacitors and their application" *J. Power. Sources.* Vol. 97–98, pp. 807-811, 2001.
- [7] V. V. N. Obreja, "On the performance of supercapacitors with electrodes based on carbon nanotubes and carbon activated material-A review" *Physica. E* Vol. 40, No.7, pp. 2596-2605, 2008.
- [8] Y. Gogotsi and P. Simon, "True Performance Metrics in Electrochemical Energy Storage" *Science* Vol. 334, No.18, pp.917-918, 2011.
- [9] M. Winter and R. J. Brodd, "What Are Batteries, Fuel Cells, and Supercapacitors?" *Chem. Rev.* Vol. 104, pp.4245-4269, 2004.
- [10] J. Li, X. Wang, Q. Huang, S. Gamboa and P. J. Sebastian, "Studies on preparation and performances of carbon aerogel electrodes for the application of supercapacitor" *J. Power. Sources.* Vol. 158, No.1, pp.784-788, 2006.
- [11] A. Burke, "Ultracapacitors: why, how, and where is the technology" *J. Power. Sources.* Vol. 91, No.1, pp.37-50, 2000.
- [12] J. R. Miller and P. Simon, "Electrochemical Capacitors for Energy Management" *Science* Vol. 321, No. 1, pp.651-652, 2008.
- [13] P. Simon and Y. Gogotsi, "Materials for electrochemical capacitors" *Nat. Mater.* Vol.7, No.11, pp.845-854, 2008.
- [14] S. Vaddiraju, H. I. Cebeci, K. K. Gleason and B. L. Wardle, *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* Vol. 1, No. 11, pp.2565–2572, 2009.
- [15] G.A. Snook, P. Kao and A.S. Best, "Conducting-polymer-based supercapacitor devices and electrodes". *J Power Sources* Vol. 196, No.1, pp.1-12, 2011.
- [16] V. Gupta and N. Miura, "Polyaniline/single-wall carbon nanotube (PANI/SWCNT) composites for high performance supercapacitors". *Electrochim Acta* Vol. 52, No. 4, pp.1721-1726, 2006.
- [17] B. L. Wardle, D. S. Saito, E. J. Garcia, A. J. Hart, R. G. de Villoria and E. A. Verploegen, "Fabrication and Characterization of Ultrahigh-Volume- Fraction Aligned Carbon Nanotube–Polymer Composites" *Adv. Mater.* Vol. 20, No. 14, pp. 2707-2714, 2008.
- [18] D. N. Futaba, K. Hata, T. Yamada, T. Hiraoka, Y. Hayamizu, Y. Kakudate, O. Tanaike, H. Hatori, M. Yumura and S. Iijima, "Shape-engineerable and highly densely packed single-walled carbon nanotubes and their

application as super-capacitor electrodes”, *Nat. Mater.* Vol. 5, No. 12, pp. 987-994, 2006.

[19] Z. Fan, J. Yan, T. Wei, L. Zhi, G. Ning, T. Li, et al. “Asymmetric supercapacitors based on graphene/MnO₂ and activated carbon nanofiber electrodes with high power and energy density.” *Adv Funct Mater* Vol. 21 No. 21, pp. 2366-2375, 2011.

[20] I. Stein, SM Thesis, Dept. of Aeronautics and Astronautics, MIT, June 2013.